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HISTORY

Asteroid 433 Eros, Part 1

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On August 13, 1898, astronomers Gustav Witt and Auguste H.B. Charlois independently discovered an asteroid which would become a focal point of numerous studies throughout the next century, 433 Eros. Eros was the first near-Earth asteroid (NEA) to be discovered, crossing the orbit of Mars, and is amongst the largest NEAs in the solar system. 433 completes its orbit around the Sun every 1.76 years or 643 days and rotates on its axis once every 5.270 hours. Containing siliceous materials, Eros is an S-type asteroid which is the most common type of asteroid found in the inner solar system. [\[1\]](#)

Many of the studies of Eros have involved the Harvard College Observatory (HCO) at their core. The first of these studies was undertaken in order to produce a more accurate ephemeris for Eros. An ephemeris is a model that predicts the position of an object in the sky at a certain time and location. [\[2\]](#) The ephemeris of Eros would become crucial for a later study which made use of the information generated here to calculate the distance from the Earth to the Sun.

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The ephemeris study of Eros was led by [Seth Carlo Chandler](#) and [Williamina Fleming](#) at the HCO, with the predetermined goal of having an accurate ephemeris for the measurements of the upcoming opposition project of 1901 (described in the [next post](#)). Chandler had created a very rough ephemeris of the path of Eros, but there was a very large degree of uncertainty in the predicted positions. As a result, astronomers would not know exactly what area of the sky to image when photographing Eros. [3] Fleming carried out an extensive analysis and examined over 1300 square degrees of data in plates by eye.[4] For comparison, the entire sky is about 41000 square degrees, so Fleming analyzed about three percent of the entire sky. Eventually, 21 non-spectral plates of Eros were found, many of which were labeled with the asteroid and comparison stars used to measure its position.[5] This allowed for a more precise ephemeris to be calculated. In this process, additional images of asteroids [Flora](#) and [Nysa](#) were found, and two new variable stars were discovered.[6] Below are photographs of the plates and jackets of four plates that Fleming had found. These plates can still be found at the HCO today.

Handwritten blue scribble at the top of the page.

Handwritten notes in black ink, including symbols like 'y', 'x', 'z', 'B', 'n', and 'a' with various lines and arrows connecting them.

Planet (B2) 433.

RA = $9^{\text{h}} 20^{\text{m}} 30^{\text{s}}$ - $30^{\circ} 40'$ (approx 1855)

No. B 10951

CLASS L

R. A. 9 10

DEC. $-17^{\circ} 30'$

QUALITY. 3

April 18, 1894.

Circ 36

	δ	μ	α	β	γ
1 = BD -13° 2852	9	19	43.8	-13° 38.7	8.8 ✓
2 = BD -13° 2855	9	19	47.8	-13 51.5	7.8 ✓
3 = BD -13° 2857	9	20	13.7	-13 42.7	9.0 ✓
4 = BD -13° 2858	9	20	15.7	-13° 16.6	7.8 ✓
5 = BD -13° 2859	9	20	24.4	-13° 21.9	9.4 ✓
6 = BD -13° 2861	9	20	59.3	-13 49.5	10 ✓

$\gamma = \text{RD} -13^{\circ} 28' 22'' \text{ } 9 \text{ } 21 \text{ } 8.8 -13 \text{ } 51.4 \text{ } 9.51$

Above are plate B 10951 and its jacket. Eros is labeled on the plate, and comparison stars are shown on both the plate and jacket.

~~Special box - for Eros~~
Planet 433 (D2) seen

No. I 10,315
CLASS L
R. A. h. 3^h 26^m
DEC. 15^o 53^s
QUALITY 3
Taken Dec. 19, 93.
Compare with I 20321 14^m Exp.
Cu36

Above are plate I 10215 and its jacket. Eros and the comparison stars used in the ephemeris study are marked on the plate.

Planet 433 (D. L.) seen
 Compare with I 3115.

No. I 10321
 CLASS, L
 R. A. 7 24
 DEC. + 48. 4
 QUALITY, 3
 DATE, Dec 27-1893
 EXPOSURE, 2

Above are plate I 10321 and its jacket. Eros and comparison stars used in the study are marked on the plate.

		No. <u>B 15531</u>	
		CLASS. <u>L</u>	
		R. A. <u>18 50</u>	
		DEC. <u>-37.5</u>	
		QUALITY. <u>3</u>	
		DATE <u>April 6 1896</u>	
		EXPOSURE. <u>60^m</u>	
<u>13c</u>	<u>18^h 2076</u>	<u>18^h 36^m 6.80</u>	<u>-38° 33'</u>
<u>23c</u>	<u>18 2163</u>	<u>37 31.79</u>	<u>-38 14' 58.3"</u>
<u>33c</u>	<u>18 2005</u>	<u>34 43.12</u>	<u>-38 33 29.3</u>
<u>43c</u>	<u>18 2009</u>	<u>34 45.55</u>	<u>-38 44 56.5</u>
<u>53c</u>	<u>18 2118</u>	<u>36 48.03</u>	<u>-37 59 44.5</u>
<u>73c</u>	<u>18 2134</u>	<u>37 2.81</u>	<u>-37 57 46.7</u>

Above are plate B 15531 and its jacket. Eros is labeled on the plate. Comparison stars used in the ephemeris study are marked and written on the jacket.

Additionally, Henry Norris Russell recalculated and further enhanced the ephemeris of Chandler one year later. His calculations combined those of Chandler and additional measurements taken by Washburn Observatory. This further refined the ephemeris of Eros. [7]

The ephemeris project in 1899 would prove to be an invaluable asset. Having the knowledge of the exact orbital properties of Eros would be required when refining the astronomical unit. This would become the next major project to feature this asteroid just one year later.

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<http://adsabs.harvard.edu/full/1899AJ.....20....8R>
3. Jones, Bessie Zaban, and Lyle Gifford Boyd. The Harvard College Observatory: The First Four Directorships, 1839-1919. Cambridge, MA: Harvard UP, 1971. Print. pp343-344.
4. Pickering, Edward Charles. "Witt's Planet (433), DQ." Witt's Planet (433), DQ. The SAO/NASA Astrophysics Data System, 1899. Web. 12 July 2013.
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6. Pickering, Edward Charles. "Witt's Planet (433), DQ." Witt's Planet (433), DQ. The SAO/NASA Astrophysics Data System, 1899. Web. 12 July 2013.
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7. Russell, Henry Norris. "Elements and Ephemeris of (433) Eros" 1899AJ.....20....8R Page 8. The SAO/NASA Astrophysics Data System, 1899. Web. 15 July 2013.
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Asteroid 433 Eros, Part 2

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